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Masalaning berilgan qiymatlarini va topishimiz mumkin bo'lgan qiymatlarni jadval ko'rinishida yozib olamiz.

a	b	c	m ₁	m ₂	m ₃	m ₄	G	R _c	Θ	M _K	τ	φ	θ
(m)	(m)	(m)	kN · m	kN · m	kN · m	kN · m	GPa	MPa	°/m	kN · m	MPa		
0,8	0,5	1,6	13	10	22	7	80	130	3,0	–	–	–	–

Yechish:

AB uchastka uchun:

$$M_{K_{AB}} = -m_1 = -13 \text{ kN} \cdot \text{m}$$

BC uchastka uchun:

$$M_{K_{BC}} = -m_1 + m_2 = -13 + 10 = -3 \text{ kN} \cdot \text{m}$$

CD uchastka uchun:

$$M_{K_{CD}} = -m_1 + m_2 - m_3 = -13 + 10 - 22 = -25 \text{ kN} \cdot \text{m}$$

DE uchastka uchun:

$$M_{K_{DE}} = -m_1 + m_2 - m_3 - m_4 = -13 + 10 - 22 - 7 = -32 \text{ kN} \cdot \text{m}$$

$$M_{K_{\max}} = 32 \text{ kN} \cdot \text{m}$$

$$1). \quad \tau_{\max} = \frac{M_{K_{\max}}}{W_{\rho}} \leq [\tau] - \text{buralishda mustahkamlik sharti}$$

$$\tau_{\max} = \frac{M_{K_{\max}}}{W_{\rho}} = \frac{16 \cdot M_{K_{\max}}}{\pi \cdot d^3} \leq R_c$$

$$W_{\rho} = \frac{\pi \cdot d^3}{16} - \text{val kesimining qutb qarshilik momenti}$$

Valning mustahkamlik shartini qanoatlantiruvchi zaruriy diametrini aniqlaymiz:

$$d_{\tau} \geq \sqrt[3]{\frac{16 \cdot M_{K_{\max}}}{\pi \cdot R_c}} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{16 \cdot 32 \cdot 10^3}{3,14 \cdot 130 \cdot 10^6}} = 0,108 \text{ m} = 10,8 \text{ sm}$$

$$2). \quad \theta = \frac{M_{K_{\max}}}{G \cdot I_{\rho}} \leq [\theta] - \text{buralishda bikirlik sharti}$$

$$I_{\rho} = \frac{\pi d^4}{32}$$

$$\theta = \frac{32 \cdot M_{K_{\max}}}{G \cdot \pi \cdot d^4} \leq [\theta],$$

$$[\theta] = 3,0^{\circ}/\text{m} \cdot \frac{\pi}{180^{\circ}} = 0.0523 \text{ rad/m}$$

Valning bikirlik shartini qanoatlantiruvchi zaruriy diametrini aniqlaymiz:

$$d_{\theta} \geq \sqrt[4]{\frac{32 \cdot M_{K_{\max}}}{G \cdot \pi \cdot [\theta]}} = \sqrt[4]{\frac{32 \cdot 32 \cdot 10^3}{80 \cdot 10^9 \cdot 3,14 \cdot 0.0523}} = 0,0369 \text{ m} = 3,69 \text{ sm}$$

Yaxlitlangan $d \approx 12,5 \text{ sm} = 125 \text{ mm}$ deb qabul qilamiz

$$\boxed{d \approx 12,5 \text{ sm} = 125 \text{ mm}}$$

Doiraviy kesimli sserjenni qutb qarshilik momentini aniqlaymiz

$$W_{\rho} = \frac{\pi \cdot d^3}{16} = \frac{3,14 \cdot 12,5^3}{16} = 383,301 \text{ sm}^3 = 383,301 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3$$

Sterjen kesimining qutb inersiya momentini aniqlaymiz

$$I_{\rho} = \frac{\pi \cdot d^4}{32} = \frac{3,14 \cdot 12,5^4}{32} = 2395,63 \text{ sm}^4 = 2395,63 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ m}^4$$

Har bir oraliqdagi sterjenning urinma kuchlanishlarini aniqlaymiz

$$\tau_{AB} = \frac{M_{K_{AB}}}{W_{\rho}} = \frac{-13 \cdot 10^3}{383,301 \cdot 10^{-6}} = -33,92 \text{ MPa}$$

$$\tau_{BC} = \frac{M_{K_{BC}}}{W_{\rho}} = \frac{-3 \cdot 10^3}{383,301 \cdot 10^{-6}} = -7,83 \text{ MPa}$$

$$\tau_{CD} = \frac{M_{K_{CD}}}{W_{\rho}} = \frac{-25 \cdot 10^3}{383,301 \cdot 10^{-6}} = -65,22 \text{ MPa}$$

$$\tau_{DE} = \frac{M_{K_{DE}}}{W_{\rho}} = \frac{-32 \cdot 10^3}{383,301 \cdot 10^{-6}} = -83,49 \text{ MPa}$$

Har bir oraliqdagi buralish burchagini Guk qonunidan foydalanib aniqlaymiz

$$\varphi = \frac{M_K \cdot \ell}{G \cdot I_{\rho}}$$

$$I_{\rho} = \frac{\pi \cdot d^4}{32} = \frac{3,14 \cdot 12,5^4}{32} = 2395,63 \text{ sm}^4 = 2395,63 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ m}^4$$

$$\varphi_{DE} = \frac{M_{K_{DE}} \cdot a}{G \cdot I_{\rho}} = \frac{-32 \cdot 10^3 \cdot 0,8}{80 \cdot 10^9 \cdot 2395,63 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ m}^4} = -0,0134 \text{ rad}$$

$$\varphi_{CD} = \frac{M_{K_{CD}} \cdot c}{G \cdot I_{\rho}} = \frac{-25 \cdot 10^3 \cdot 1,6}{80 \cdot 10^9 \cdot 2395,63 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ m}^4} = -0,0209 \text{ rad}$$

$$\varphi_{BC} = \frac{M_{K_{BC}} \cdot b}{G \cdot I_{\rho}} = \frac{-3 \cdot 10^3 \cdot 0,5}{80 \cdot 10^9 \cdot 2395,63 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ m}^4} = -0,0008 \text{ rad}$$

$$\varphi_{AB} = \frac{M_{K_{AB}} \cdot a}{G \cdot I_{\rho}} = \frac{-13 \cdot 10^3 \cdot 0,8}{80 \cdot 10^9 \cdot 2395,63 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ m}^4} = -0,0054 \text{ rad}$$

Valni o'ng uchining buralish burchagi nolga teng ekanligi ma'lum.

$$\varphi_E = 0$$

$$\varphi_D = \varphi_E + \varphi_{DE} = -0,0134 \text{ rad}$$

$$\varphi_C = \varphi_D + \varphi_{CD} = -0,0134 - 0,0209 = -0,0343 \text{ rad}$$

$$\varphi_B = \varphi_C + \varphi_{BC} = -0,0343 - 0,0008 = -0,0351 \text{ rad}$$

$$\varphi_A = \varphi_B + \varphi_{AB} = -0,0351 - 0,0054 = -0,0405 \text{ rad}$$

Nisbiy buralish burchagi quyidagicha topiladi

$$\theta = \frac{\varphi}{\ell}$$

$$\theta_{AB} = \frac{\varphi_{AB}}{a} = \frac{-0,0054}{0,8} = -0,00675 \text{ rad}$$

$$\theta_{BC} = \frac{\varphi_{BC}}{b} = \frac{-0,0008}{0,7} = -0,00114 \text{ rad}$$

$$\theta_{CD} = \frac{\varphi_{CD}}{c} = \frac{-0,0209}{1,6} = -0,0131 \text{ rad}$$

$$\theta_{DE} = \frac{\varphi_{DE}}{a} = \frac{-0,0134}{0,8} = -0,0168 \text{ rad}$$

Buralishda mustahkamlik sharti bajarildi

$$\tau_{\max} = 83.49 \text{ MPa} < R_C = 130 \text{ MPa}$$

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